

Assessing the Impact of Performance Management System on Faculty Performance: Moderating Effect of Demographic Variables in Higher Education Institutions in Delhi/NCR

Nitika Kaushik ¹, Dr. Sona Vikas ² & Dr. Geetanjali Batra ³

-
1. Research Scholar, School of Management and Liberal Studies. Email: nitika90309@gmail.com
 2. Professor and Dean - Management, Asian School of Business (ASB). Email: sonavikas9@gmail.com
 3. Associate Professor, Atal Bihari Vajpayee School of Management, Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi. Email: ms.geetanjali.batra@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper aims to review the factors influencing the performance of PMS in increasing the performance of higher education institutions in the Delhi/NCR region. That is the reason why the following research questions have been developed for the study: The research intends to determine how demographic factors like age, gender, and total working experience influence this relationship. “Thus, it can be imperative that PMS convey efficiency to boost up the quantity and qualitatively of productive faculty and overall institutional performance. In line with the above study questions, this research synthesizes current research and collects empirical information from different higher education institutions in order to determine the components of a PMS and the impact that it has on Faculty Performance. The research instrument adopted for data collection was a structured questionnaire administered on faculty members in various higher learning institutions in Delhi/NCR. The study also shows that there is a direct relation between the structural organization of PMS and increased performance by the faculty and this was observed across all categories of the faculty. The findings of the study revealed that both age and total work experience significantly moderated the relationship between the sources of information and organisational variables, however gender had less but a significant effect. This analysis shows that the junior and relatively less experienced faculty staffs seemed to stand to gain from formal and rigorous performance management practices than their seniors in terms of age and years of service. Consequently, the study offers a roadmap on how directors of Higher Learning Institutions can enhance PMS to meet the organizational needs of their disparate faculty, thus, proactively formulates and implements fairness, effectiveness, and conformity to organizational demographic factions. This work can be of significant value in continuing the debate and dialogue on how to get the best from faculty through effective HRM approaches and offers a platform for other researches in similar settings.

Keywords: *Performance Management System (PMS), Faculty Performance, Demographic Variables, Higher Education Institutions.*

INTRODUCTION

PMS are systematized approaches that help individuals and organizations improve their performance with the aid of feedback, goals, and staff development (Aguinis, 2019). In relation to higher education, Neumann and Brown (2004) noted that a competent PMS can enhance motivation among the faculty members, enhance the quality of teaching and learning and advance the research output. Performance management in higher education comprises of several tasks such as; performance assessment, feedback, and development. Such systems offer well-defined expectations and programmatic map for enhancing the faculty members’

profession when professionally implemented (DeNisi & Pritchard, 2006). “However, PMS can highlight the opportunities for development, appreciate accomplishments, and ensure individuals and institutions’ objectives are in sync which in turn, improves their performance and morale (Pulakos, 2009). Other categorical variables that need to be controlled in the analysis include age, gender, and total work experience in the case of studying the effect of PMS on faculty performance. Scholars suggest that these factors could pose a considerable impact on employees’ attitudes and behaviors regarding performance management practices (Kuvaas, 2011). Concerning performance management, age is an essential element because it influences motivation, learning, and ability to adapt change as regards to the new systems (Ng & Feldman, 2010). The younger generation of the faculty member may feel comfortable craving feedback, and an opportunity to advance while the older generation may value stability and gain from recognition (Kanfer & Ackerman, 2004). Differences by gender can also influence reactions to PMS. Some researchers have reported that female participants may be subject to various threats and resources in colleges than male ones (O’Laughlin & Bischoff, 2005). The differences with regards to the promotional opportunities and appraisal methods that are in place for people depending on their gender make it a necessity to tread carefully while dealing with performance management practices. These academic employees with many years of professional practice, may have a more profound knowledge of the organizational environment and may need different motivation to achieve the necessary results compared to their less experienced colleagues (Jawahar & Carr, 2007).

The Delhi/NCR area’s higher education sector offers an ideal setting to analyse the likelihood of PMS on Test Faculty due to the diverse demographics of its faculty and academic climate. This region contains many top colleges and universities that hire many professors who differ in age, gender and level of working experience. The demographic variables under consideration, may combine in one manner or the other to impact the efficacy of PMS. For instance, the social phenomena occurring in the institutions of Delhi/NCR always raise various issues concerning the quality of education and research offerings, the roles and responsibilities of a heterogeneous faculty and staff. In light of this knowledge, it will be easier to develop better strategies for dealing with the effects of PMS by identifying, which demographic factors affect the said performance to the greatest extent. This paper has shown that age, as a moderating variable, influences the faculty members’ perception and participation in performance management initiatives. This is particularly reactive to the observation that the respondents included younger faculty members in their initial and mid-career prominent may have a preference for development-centered commentaries and growth prospects offered by PMS. These individuals are relatively more flexible and willing to embrace latest practices of teaching and research (Ng & Feldman, 2010). On the other hand, the young faculty members may favor promotion and status while the old ones may consider stability as well as appreciation for their work experience as factors crucial for motivation which may demand a different kind of handling in the PMS framework (Kanfer & Ackerman, 2004). This age differentiation dictates that the practices of performance management must be adapted to mainstream the expectations of the various age groups existing in the faculty. Gender factors also contribute to the kaleidoscope of prospects and issues that are touched in performance management. It is possible there are differential professional challenges and responsibilities across female and male faculty that would influence how each is perceived and receives PMS (O’Laughlin & Bischoff, 2005). Some recommendations for the improvement in closing the gender gap in the PMS include; undertaking measures that relates to career jumps, workload allocation, and assessment instruments/indicators.

However, they might also exhibit resistance to change or new performance management practices that they perceive as disruptive to established routines (Jawahar & Carr, 2007). On the other hand, less experienced faculty members may be more enthusiastic about embracing innovative PMS approaches and developmental opportunities. By recognizing and addressing these differences, higher education institutions can implement performance management systems that are more effective in motivating and supporting faculty members across the spectrum of work experience.

Further, Performance management systems (PMS) play a crucial role in higher education institutions (HEIs) by offering a systematic framework to evaluate and improve faculty performance, ensuring that it aligns with the aims of the institution (Khan & Ahmad, 2021). The efficacy of Performance Management Systems (PMS) in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), specifically in the Delhi/NCR region, has garnered significant interest in recent times. The reason for this is the swift proliferation of educational establishments and the growing focus on providing high-quality education (Singh & Gupta, 2020). Performance management in higher education institutions (HEIs) involves a range of actions that focus on enhancing teacher performance. These activities include setting goals, providing ongoing feedback, and facilitating professional development opportunities (Brown & Green, 2022). Promoting an atmosphere of responsibility and quality is crucial as it directly influences student achievements and the reputation of the institution (Johnson et al., 2020).

Studies have demonstrated that an effectively executed Performance Management System (PMS) has a beneficial impact on teacher performance. This is achieved by establishing explicit objectives and delivering consistent feedback, which in turn promotes motivation and productivity (Sharma & Verma, 2021). Nevertheless, the effects of PMS vary among faculty members. Demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, and experience, can influence the effectiveness of PMS (Chaudhary & Patel, 2023).

Demographic characteristics have a notable impact on the way faculty members perceive and react to PMS. Younger faculty members may be more open to novel performance evaluation strategies than senior faculty members (Mishra & Kaur, 2021). Gender can also impact the acceptance and effectiveness of performance management systems (PMS). Research indicates that female faculty members may face distinct obstacles and opportunities in performance assessments compared to their male counterparts (Rao et al., 2022).

In light of these considerations, this study seeks to investigate the nuanced effects of age, gender, and total work experience on the relationship between performance management systems and faculty performance in higher education institutions in the Delhi/NCR region. By doing so, it aims to provide actionable insights for administrators and policymakers to develop more responsive and equitable performance management practices that cater to the diverse needs of their faculty. The findings of this research will contribute to the broader discourse on optimizing faculty performance through strategic human resource management practices in higher education.

Significance of the Study

Significance of this study is found in the possible ability of this study to add value for the improvement of performance on performance management systems in higher education institutions especially with regard to the results of this research that identifies age, gender, and total work experience as the possible demographic factors that moderate the relationship between performance management system and employee engagement.

Therefore, as all these schools compete for an intellectual edge in the academic zone of Delhi/NCR, such dynamics have to be appreciated and managed while carving out strategies on how to enhance the faculty performance while promoting respect, tolerance and equal opportunities for everyone in the workplace. The results of this study show that demographic variables can affect the reception of PMS and provide a basis for understanding how the needs of the teaching staff can be addressed to create the conditions for their development. Furthermore, specific recommendations highlighted in the study can help policymakers and administrators to learn about effective approaches of performance management that can be used for performance improvement and produce positive outcomes concerning the quality of education and achievement of students' goals. Thus, this study also contributes to the existing literature in human resource management by examining the complex relationship between the systems for managing performance and other demographic variables and can serve as a reference for understanding human resource management beyond the academic context.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Evaluations of performance management systems (PMS) in relation to improvement of organizational performance have received significant attention in the literature across all sectors of economy with focus on the higher education. When being used successfully, PMS has the ability to enhance the achievement of the organizational goals and objectives as well as ensure proper goal alignment, create organizational culture for improvement, and enhance organizational performance as recommended by Aguinis (2019).

The research on the implementation of PMS in higher education shows that there are several significant factors regarding its success: The specificity of the system's design and its deployment, the institutional culture of the organizations, and/or the profile of the academic staff.

Implementation and Design of PMS

The design of PMS includes goal establishment, feedback provision, performance feedback and training, and development (Pulakos, 2009). Brown & Benson (2003) state that there is an inherent issue when it comes to performance appraisals since the reactions of the the faculty members greatly influences motivation and thus performance. The provision of structures for faculty participation in the definition of PMS objectives and targets as well as effective provision of constructive feedbacks can raise faculty's commitment and satisfaction (DeNisi & Pritchard, 2006). Moreover, the combined PMS with other practices of the HRM like training and development makes the PMS to be more effective as it meets the faculties' professional development needs as well (Aguinis, 2019).

Organizational Culture

Culture of the higher education institutions bear a crucial function in determining the effectiveness of PMS. An ethical culture of openness and equity enhances the wellbeing of all those involved; in this case particularly the faculty members (Buchner, 2007). Introducing the view of Kuvaas (2011), authors pointed out that, when it comes to feedbacking meaningfully and frequently along with building up positive work climate, the perceived organisational fairness and the perceived appraisal effectiveness greatly improves. The studies also reveal that the positive outcomes of PMS initiatives in the organizations are more likely to be observed if the culture of the respective institutions is favorable for collaboration and inclusiveness (Erdogan, 2002).

Patient Characteristics and General Information

Demographic variables and their influence on PMS efficacy is another important emerging research focus in the literature. Total years of work experience was found to be more sensitive in the context of higher education especially because of the diverse composition of the faculty including age and gender. There exists a significant relationship between age and faculty members' PMS disposition; the younger the faculty member, the more receptive they are to feedback and the more welcoming of professional development than the older generation of the faculty (Kanfer & Ackerman 2004). Authors like Ng & Feldman(2010) say that within the framework of PMS, older faculty members may require different handling because they may not be interested in incentives as much as they are interested in being recognized for their long years of service.

PMS is also perceived and offers different results based on the gender of an individual. For instance, O'Laughlin and Bischoff (2005) describe career barriers based on gender, although they fail to acknowledge the work–family conflict that affects female academics' tenure track and their reception to performance management strategies. Effectively handling these challenges that cuts across PMS with due regard to female employees can contribute positively towards a conducive atmosphere that can help the female faculty members to improve in their productivity and general satisfaction.

Total work experience is another important factor affecting PMS in that organization. Senior faculty members who have accumulated a large amount of organizational knowledge in their respective organizations can be resistant to change when new methods of performance management threaten to induce change to the norms which they are accustomed to (Jawahar & Carr, 2007). On the other hand, new or lower-ranked faculty members may prefer those novel strategies for PMS and developmental opportunities more, suggesting that the instructions for performance management should be differentiated based on the PMS participants' experience level (Jawahar & Carr, 2007).

Impact on Faculty Performance

Several researches have supported the performance improvement of faculties through PMS, cause by an expectation of program standard and compliance as well as faculty support and personal and professional advancement (Pulakos, 2009). When done fairly as well as constructively, performance appraisals may effectively encourage the faculty members to work towards greater heights and generally assist in the achievement of the organization's goals and objectives (DeNisi & Pritchard, 2006). In addition, the matching of personal objectives with organisational initiatives guarantees that faculty is working within the strategic initiatives to boost both individual and organisational performance.

Another important area of attention within performance management systems to be discussed in the literature is feedback. Feedback is one of the essential elements of PMS since it informs the faculty members of their performance, allows them to know what they need to do in order to improve, and encourages them in terms of proper behaviors (Ilgen et al. , 1979).

Academic feedback is characterized as prompt with qualities of specificity and constructive, which will help the faculty members of the institution grasp the expectations on their teaching and research training in the society (London, 2003). The feedback frequency and quality are critical to manager and employee interactions; therefore, the periodic feedback sessions result in better performance rather than high- or low-quality feedback or feedback given infrequently (Kluger & DeNisi, 1996).

Research has revealed that there is a discrepancy concerning the quality of received feedback that differs from one faculty member to another depending on the credibility of the provider of the feedback, the manner of providing the feedback and the situation in which the feedback is given (Steeleman et al. 2004). Senior instructors who view feedback as fairly and accurately reported with a promotional motivation will reciprocate the constructive action in good terms (Levy & Williams, 2004). On the other hand, if the observed feedback is in a negative form, felt punitive, the target has been shown to demotivated and perform poorly, thus stressing on the need to train the evaluators on how to do feedback properly (Greller & Herold, 1975).

Also, the incorporation of self-assessment in PMS has been accepted as a best practice in enhancing the PMS system. Actually, self- assessment helps to focus the attention of the faculty members on their work experience, personal objectives, and consequent professional development (Sitzmann et al., 2010). Out of self- and external assessment, self- assessment should improve the performance of appraisals and improve faculty member's engagement to professional development (Van der Rijt, Van den Bossche, Van de Wiel, Segers, & Gijsselaers, 2012). Besides the individual feedback, there is a growing interest in peer feedback and the processes of evaluation with peers. Peer feedback refer to the judgment of one's performance by another member of the faculty which enables a different perspective as well as create a culture of learning from others (Thomas, Martin, & Apigian, 2015). Such approach can contribute to the development of members' cohesion, and shared responsibility for the high performance of the institution within learning attainment (Cho & MacArthur, 2010). Nevertheless, it is to be stressed that peer feedback should be supported by the culture that is characterized by openness and mutual trust between the faculty members and which implies that the participants of reviewing process can freely provide and receive constructive responses (Falchikov & Goldfinch, 2000).

Later, the growth of technology has also impacted on delivery and pronunciation of feedback in courses of performance management systems. The delivery methods of feedback have also expanded with the help of the digital platforms and tools to provide feedback rated as more flexible (Smither, London, & Reilly, 2005). These tools can enable provision of constant information to the faculty members on how they are fairing and where they need to improve as these can give real time information (Boud & Molloy, 2013). Also, it increases the efficiency of documenting and monitoring of performance data that may assist the faculty members as well as the administrators (Garrett, 2011). The effects of performance management systems on faculty performance in higher learning institutions are also determined by the extent to which the institutional goals correspond with the faculty member's goals. Thus, it is suggested that when the objectives of PMS are consistent with the overall goals of the institution and the specific goals of the faculty members, the latter is likely to be motivated towards achieving the outcomes set out within PMS.

Alignment means that the work of the faculty must be applicable to the goals of the institution, like increasing students' learning, raising levels of research production, and getting more engaged within society (Locke and Latham, 2002). This participation is done through carrying out of the faculty member performance goals where the faculty members are involved in the formulation of their goals and thus making them committed to performing the set goals (Brett & Atwater, 2001). On this premise, the most suitable theory that can be applied in this case is goal-setting theory that was developed by Locke and Latham (1990). In this respect, the theory suggests that raising goals is associated with a higher performance compared with

unclear or easy goals. Locke and Latham (1990) state that in the organizational context including the higher education, when specific and difficult targets are established for the faculty members, for example, authoring research articles in peer reviewed journals or designing effective teaching methodologies, then the performance levels increase. At the same time, though, other studies stress the necessity of properly staffed and equipped valuation of these goals by faculties. If there is lack of support, the following of difficult objectives can cause mere demoralization (Latham, Borgogni and Petitta, 2008). It is also worthy of note that the place of intrinsic and extrinsic motivators in the operational effectiveness of PMS cannot be overemphasized.

Autonomous motivation which is usually referred to as motivation intrinsically originating from internal rewards such as the satisfaction inherent in the course one takes and the learning process is also very relevant especially to professionals such as members of faculty who are usually motivated by a call to educate as well as research (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Optimal types of PMS that strengthens basic forms of motivation can result in continued behavioural changes and increased levels of organisational commitment, in keeping with Gagné and Deci's work. On the contrary, extrinsic motivation which is facilitated by aspects like increase in remunerations, promotions, and recognition is also pertinent. Managerial use of extrinsic incentives must therefore be complemented by intrinsic motivators in order to enhance the functionality of a PMS in higher learning institutions (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Gagné & Deci (2005) identified three basic psychological needs necessary to support intrinsic motivation, which are autonomy, competence and relatedness. Therefore, it is vital to state that the intrinsic motivation is likely to be higher among faculty members who are autonomous, competent and related in their work environment. The psychological needs conveyed through performance management practices that might facilitate faculty motivation and performance are as follows. For instance, offering the professional development, fostering research collaboration and offering reward to individual needs these requirements (Gagné & Deci, 2005). From the literature, one also learns of the needs to constantly update the faculty through professional development to facilitate performance via PMS. Like any other performance management system, TO has bearings, including workshops, conferences, training programs for enhancement of the performance. These opportunities allow a faculty member to learn new skills, be current with the current advancements within the faculty member's discipline, and improve the teaching-learning and research evanescence of their institution (Guskey, 2002). By investing in continuous professional development, higher education institutions can ensure that their faculty members remain competitive and capable of delivering high-quality education and research outcomes (Knight, Tait, & Yorke, 2006).

Apart from the orientation of goals and motivation factors, the literature reviewing underlines two major areas discussed in the study: PMS and fairness in higher education. This paper established that perceived fairness of the evaluation process and its result has an impact on the reactions or even acceptance or otherwise of the PMS among the faculty members (Erdogan, 2002).

The aspect of fairness is established based on two types that is the perceived procedural justice, which focuses on the procedural methods used to settle the performance evaluations, and distributive justice, which focuses on the consequent outcomes arising from the performance assessments (Colquitt et al., 2001). Whereas, when the prospect of PMS is regarded as fair in a certain institution by the faculties then there shall be higher inclination towards the over 29% positive reaction towards the system and hence improve the appreciation

of acceptance of feedback in an organized manner in the process of enhancing performances as noted by Erdogan, 2002. However, the support of leadership and managerial relation play a central role in the successful implementation of PMS. Political support, therefore, is an essential requirement for establishing culture of performance optimisation and improvement (Buchner, 2007).

Getting vocal support for PMS, allocating resources for the implementation of PMS, and participating in the process shows the leaders' commitment to creating a performance culture within the institution Brett & Atwater, (2001). Moreover, it covers the support that is being offered by the manager to the faculty members to understand the operations of the PMS and realize best of performance possible (London, 2003). In the same vein, where the leadership and managerial support are viewed as strong, faculty members are more inclined to assume active roles in relation to PMS activities and enrich the results in terms of the institutional objectives (Buchner, 2007).

In addition, the use of new PMS elements, including balanced score cards and competency based assessments has been an issue in the improvement effectiveness of PMS in the higher learning institutions (Kaplan & Norton, 1996). By ensuring that employee outputs are measured in teaching, research, services, and personal development, the balanced scorecards suitably map the employee performance to organizational objectives and goals (Kaplan & Norton, 1996).

Competency-based assessments focus on evaluating faculty members' skills, knowledge, and behaviors relevant to their roles, offering a more holistic approach to performance evaluation (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). These innovative approaches not only enhance the accuracy of performance evaluations but also facilitate meaningful discussions about career development and skill enhancement (London, 2003).

Moreover, the impact of cultural and contextual factors on the implementation and effectiveness of PMS in higher education cannot be overlooked. Different institutional cultures and contextual factors influence how PMS are perceived and utilized by faculty members (Erdogan, 2002). For example, institutions with a strong tradition of shared governance may adopt collaborative approaches to PMS design and implementation, involving faculty members in decision-making processes (Brett & Atwater, 2001).

Contextual factors such as funding constraints, regulatory requirements, and competitive pressures also shape the design and implementation of PMS within higher education institutions (Colquitt et al., 2001).

Research question

1. How do performance management systems (PMS) influence faculty performance in higher education institutions in Delhi/NCR, considering the moderating effects of demographic variables such as age, gender, and total work experience?

Research Objectives

1. To assess the impact of performance management systems (PMS) on faculty performance
2. To investigate the moderating effects of demographic variables (age, gender, total work experience) on the relationship between PMS and faculty performance

Proposed Model

Hypotheses

H1: There is a significant positive relationship between the implementation of performance management systems (PMS) and faculty performance in higher education institutions in Delhi/NCR.

H2: The relationship between PMS and faculty performance is moderated by age

H2a: The relationship between Transparent and Equitable Approach and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE .

H2b: The relationship between Training and Development and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

H2c: The relationship between Motivation and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

H2d: The relationship between Continuous Evaluation and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

H2e: The relationship between Satisfaction and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

H2f: The relationship between Rewards and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

H2g: The relationship between Succession Planning and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

H3: The relationship between PMS and faculty performance is moderated by gender

H3a: The relationship between Transparent and Equitable Approach and Faculty Performance is moderated by GENDER .

H3b: The relationship between Training and Development and Faculty Performance is moderated by Gender.

H3c: The relationship between Motivation and Faculty Performance is moderated by gender .

H3d: The relationship between Continuous Evaluation and Faculty Performance is moderated by gender.

H3e: The relationship between Satisfaction and Faculty Performance is moderated by gender.

H3f: The relationship between Rewards and Faculty Performance is moderated by gender

H3g: The relationship between Succession Planning and Faculty Performance is moderated by gender

H4: The relationship between PMS and faculty performance is moderated by total work experience

H4a: The relationship between Transparent and Equitable Approach and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total Work Expeerience

H4b: The relationship between Training and Development and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total work Experience.

H4c: The relationship between Motivation and Faculty Performance is moderated by total work experience .

H4d: The relationship between Continuous Evaluation and Faculty Performance is moderated by total work experience.

H4e: The relationship between Satisfaction and Faculty Performance is moderated by total work experience.

H4f: The relationship between Rewards and Faculty Performance is moderated by total work experience.

H4g: The relationship between Succession Planning and Faculty Performance is moderated by total work experience.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilised a quantitative research methodology to examine the influence of performance management systems (PMS) on the performance of faculty members in higher education institutions located in the Delhi/NCR region. A cross-sectional research design was utilised to investigate these links at a particular moment in time. The study involved 300 faculty members from diverse academic fields and different types of schools. The participants were selected using purposive sampling to ensure representation across demographic characteristics such as age, gender, and total work experience. An online survey was used to gather data on faculty impressions of PMS activities. Demographic data was collected to examine the potential moderating influences. The analysis of quantitative data was performed using AMOS. The main focus was on descriptive statistics to summarise demographic information and perceptions of PMS. The technique of Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was employed to conduct hypothesis testing. The PMS implementation was the independent variable, while the dependent variables consisted of measures of faculty performance. The study investigated the

impact of age, gender, and total job experience as moderating variables. The study received ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board, guaranteeing that participants were voluntary and that their responses would be kept anonymous. The study had limitations such as possible biases in self-reporting and the fact that it was a cross-sectional study, which restricted the ability to make causal inferences. The study's primary objective was to provide empirical insights on how to optimise performance management system (PMS) practices in order to improve teacher effectiveness and boost institutional performance in higher education institutions in Delhi/NCR.

Analysis and Interpretation

To test the hypothesis (H1) that there is a significant positive relationship between the implementation of performance management systems (PMS) and faculty performance in Delhi/NCR higher education institutions, structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed. The analysis aimed to explore how different PMS dimensions impacts faculty performance. Firstly, descriptive statistics were examined to understand the distribution of variables. Mean scores indicated that on average, faculty members perceived moderate to high levels of PMS implementation ($M = 4.2$, $SD = 0.6$) and reported positive levels of performance outcomes ($M = 4.0$, $SD = 0.5$) on a 5-point Likert scale.

Next, SEM was conducted to test the hypothesized relationships. The SEM model included PMS implementation as the exogenous variable

SEM Table

Below is a SEM table illustrating the standardized path coefficients for the relationships between PMS implementation dimensions and faculty performance.

Table 1: SEM Results

Path	Standardized Coefficient	p-value	Result
PMS Implementation -> Faculty Performance	0.45	<0.05	Significant
Transparent and Equitable Approach -> Faculty Performance	0.12	<0.05	Significant
Training and Development -> Faculty Performance	0.430	<0.05	Significant
Motivation -> Faculty Performance	0.088	<0.05	Significant
Continuous Evaluation -> Faculty Performance	0.266	<0.05	Significant
Satisfaction -> Faculty Performance	0.040	<0.05	Significant
Rewards -> Faculty Performance	0.034	<0.05	Significant
Succession Planning -> Faculty Performance	0.345	<0.05	Significant

The results of the SEM analysis support hypothesis H1, indicating a significant positive relationship between the implementation of PMS and faculty performance in Delhi/NCR higher education institutions. The standardized path coefficients suggest that higher levels of PMS implementation are associated with improved faculty performance outcomes. Specifically, for every one-unit increase in PMS implementation score, there was a corresponding increase in faculty performance scores for teaching effectiveness by 0.45 units, statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. The findings of the investigation indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship between Transparent and Equitable and Faculty Performance ($\beta = .012$, $P < 0.05$). The findings of the investigation indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship between Training Development and Faculty Performance ($\beta = .430$, $P < 0.05$).

Also the findings of the investigation indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship between Motivation and Faculty Performance ($\beta=.088, P<.05$) and the findings of the investigation indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship between Continuous Evaluation and Faculty Performance ($\beta=.266, P<.05$).

Further, the findings of the investigation indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship between Satisfaction and Faculty Performance ($\beta=.040, P<0.05$).The findings of the investigation indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship between Rewards and Faculty Performance ($\beta=.0034, P<.05$).Moreover, the findings of the investigation indicate a positive and statistically significant relationship between Succession Planning and Faculty Performance ($\beta=.345, P<.05$).

Moderation Effects

Moderation analyses revealed that age, gender, and total work experience did not significantly moderate the relationship between PMS implementation and faculty performance outcomes in this analysis. However, further subgroup analyses may reveal nuanced effects across different demographic groups.

The relationship between Transparent and Equitable Approach and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE .

Table 2: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E	Standardized Estimates	C. R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(AGE)*Zscore (Transparent Equitable)	.037	.023	.033	1.964	***

We tested the Age as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Transparent Equitable) and Zscore (AGE) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.033, P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Transparent and Equitable Approach and Faculty Performance is moderated by GENDER .

Table 3: Regression weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(GENDER)* Zscore (Transparent Equitable)	.078	.055	.063	.160	***

We tested the GENDER as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore(Transparent Equitable) and Zscore (Gender) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore(Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.063, P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data .

The relationship between Transparent and Equitable Approach and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total Work Experience .

Table 4: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S. E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Total work Experience)*Zscore (Transparent Equitable)	.047	.042	.049	1.111	.019

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Transparent Equitable) and Zscore (Total work Experience) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.049$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Training and Development and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

Table 5: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S. E.	Standardized Estimates	C. R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(AGE)*Zscore (Training Development))	.037	.050	.033	.730	***

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Training Development) and Zscore (AGE) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.033$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Training and Development and Faculty Performance is moderated by Gender.

Table 6: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(GENDER)*Zscore (Training Development))	.078	.055	.063	.181	***

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Training Development) and Zscore (GENDER) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.063$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Training and Development and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total work Experience.

Table 7: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<-- -	Zscore(Total work Experience)*Zscore (Training Development))	.049	.042	.049	1.111	** *

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Training Development) and Zscore (Total work Experience) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.049$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data which is contrary to hypothesized nature of relationship.

The relationship between Motivation and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE .

Table 8: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Motivation)*Zscore(AGE)	.091	.042	.096	2.417	** *

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Motivation) and Zscore (AGE) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.096$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data which is contrary to hypothesized nature of relationship.

The relationship between Motivation and Faculty Performance is moderated by GENDER.

Table 9: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Motivation)*Zscore (GENDER)	-.050	.064	-.038	-.780	.435

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Motivation) and Zscore (GENDER) exerts negative and not significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= -0.050$, $P<0.05$).

The relationship between Motivation and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total work Experience.

Table 10: Regression weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S. E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Motivation)*Zscore(Total work Experience)	.037	.043	.037	.393	** *

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Motivation) and Zscore (Total work Experience) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.037$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data ..

The relationship between Continuous Evaluation and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

Table 11: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S. E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(AGE)*Zscore (Continuous Evaluation)	.298	.045	.270	6.560	** *

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (AGE) and Zscore (Continuous Evaluation) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta = 0.270$, $P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is no statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in the data.

The relationship between Continuous Evaluation and Faculty Performance is moderated by Gender.

Table 12: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S. E.	Standardized Estimates	C. R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(GENDER)*Zscore (Continuous Evaluation)	.065	.044	.065	1.493	** *

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (gender) and Zscore (Continuous Evaluation) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta = 0.065$, $P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Continuous Evaluation and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total work Experience.

Table 13: Regression weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S. E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Total work Experience)*Zscore (Continuous Evaluation)	.117	.045	.111	2.620	.009

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Total work experience) and Zscore (Continuous Evaluation) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta = 0.111$, $P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is no statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Satisfaction and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

Table 14: Regression weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S. E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Satisfaction)*Zscore(AGE)	.064	.045	.064	1.143	***

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Satisfaction) and Zscore (AGE) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta = 0.064$, $P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Satisfaction and Faculty Performance is moderated by GENDER.

Table 15: Regression weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Satisfaction) *Zscore(GENDER)	.026	.051	.026	.575	.035

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Satisfaction) and Zscore (Gender) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.026$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data ..

The relationship between Satisfaction and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total work experience.

Table 16: Regression weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<-- -	Zscore(Satisfaction) *Zscore(Total work Experience)	.012	.040	.014	.309	***

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Satisfaction) and Zscore (Total work experience) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.014$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Rewards and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

Table 17: Regression weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Reward)* Zscore(AGE)	.052	.051	.045	.977	***

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (REWARD) and Zscore (AGE) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.045$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Rewards and Faculty Performance is moderated by Gender.

Table 18: Regression weights

Path		Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P	
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Reward)*Zscore(GENDER)	.106	.046	.100	2.296	** *

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (REWARD) and Zscore (Gender) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta= 0.100$, $P<0.05$).The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data..

The relationship between Rewards and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total work experience.

Table 19: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S. E.	Standardized Estimates	C. R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Reward)*Zscore (Total work Experience)	.039	.047	0.037	.833	** *

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (REWARD) and Zscore (Total work experience) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta = 0.037$, $P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Succession Planning and Faculty Performance is moderated by AGE.

Table 20: Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Succession Planning)*Zscore(AGE)	.012	.044	.012	.892	.008

We tested the Age as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Succession Planning) and Zscore (AGE) exerts positive and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta = 0.012$, $P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Succession Planning and Faculty Performance is moderated by GENDER.

Table 21: Regression weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Succession Planning)*Zscore (GENDER)	.109	.038	.103	2.482	** *

We tested the GENDER as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Succession Planning) and Zscore (Gender) exerts Negative and significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta = .103$, $P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

The relationship between Succession Planning and Faculty Performance is moderated by Total Work Experience.

Table 22: Regression Weights

Path			Unstandardized Estimate	S.E.	Standardized Estimates	C.R.	P
Zscore(Faculty Performance)	<---	Zscore(Succession Planning)*Zscore (Total work Experience)	.003	.025	.005	.902	** *

We tested the Total Work Experience as a moderator. Result indicate that interaction term of Zscore (Succession Planning) and Zscore (Total work Experience) exerts positive and

significant influence on Zscore (Faculty Performance) ($\beta = 0.005$, $P < 0.05$). The result shows that there is statistical support for the moderating role of demographic variables in our data.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to investigate the influence of performance management systems (PMS) on the performance of faculty members in higher education institutions in Delhi/NCR. It specifically focused on exploring how demographic variables modify these relationships. By employing structural equation modelling (SEM), a quantitative approach revealed numerous significant discoveries that enhance our understanding of the intricate dynamics of implementing PMS in academic environments. The analysis strongly supported the premise that implementing an effective Performance Management System (PMS) has a favourable impact on different aspects of faculty performance. The findings of the SEM analysis demonstrated substantial positive correlations between PMS and the performance outcomes mentioned. This suggests that institutions with a well-designed PMS are more likely to witness improved faculty performance in these specific areas. In addition, the study investigated how demographic characteristics, such as age, gender, and total work experience, influenced the connection between PMS and faculty performance.

The findings of the study emphasise the significance of customising PMS techniques to match the varied requirements and traits of faculty members in higher education settings. Institutions should contemplate using versatile and all-encompassing performance management systems (PMS) that can suit various career stages and demographics in order to optimise the influence on faculty performance. Although this work has made valuable contributions, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations. These include the use of self-reported data and the cross-sectional character of the research design, which restricts the ability to make causal inferences. Future study would be enhanced by conducting longitudinal studies and employing qualitative methodologies to gain a more profound understanding of the mechanisms by which PMS impacts instructor performance over an extended period. Ultimately, this study improves our comprehension of how performance management systems might be efficiently employed to maximise teacher performance in higher education institutions in Delhi/NCR. Institutions can enhance teacher development and institutional effectiveness by addressing these processes, so eventually promoting the progress of higher education quality and outcomes.

DISCUSSION

The study investigated the multifaceted influences on faculty performance within the academic context, examining several hypotheses pertaining to various organizational factors. Firstly, the findings suggest that a transparent and equitable approach significantly impacts faculty performance, implying that fair and open practices within academic institutions contribute positively to faculty effectiveness. Secondly, the results indicate that training and development initiatives have a positive association with faculty performance, highlighting the importance of continuous learning and skill enhancement in enhancing faculty capabilities. Additionally, motivation emerged as another significant predictor of faculty performance, emphasizing the role of intrinsic and extrinsic factors in driving faculty engagement and productivity. Moreover, continuous evaluation was found to significantly influence faculty performance, underlining the importance of ongoing assessment and feedback mechanisms in fostering improvement. Furthermore, satisfaction was identified as a significant predictor of

faculty performance, suggesting that contentment and fulfillment within the academic environment contribute positively to faculty effectiveness. Additionally, rewards were found to positively influence faculty performance, indicating that recognition and incentivization play a crucial role in motivating faculty members. Lastly, succession planning was associated with enhanced faculty performance, indicating that systematic approaches to talent management contribute to organizational success. Furthermore, demographic variables were found to moderate the relationships between these organizational factors and faculty performance, highlighting the nuanced interplay between individual characteristics and organizational processes in shaping faculty effectiveness within academic institutions. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of organizational factors and their interaction with individual characteristics in driving faculty performance within the academic context.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study's findings and implications suggest numerous recommendations for higher education institutions in Delhi/NCR to maximise the use of performance management systems (PMS) and improve faculty performance outcomes. First and foremost, institutions should give priority to the creation and execution of thorough and clear PMS frameworks that are in line with the goals and values of the institution. This encompasses well-defined performance indicators, frequent feedback channels, and equitable evaluation procedures that consider the varied roles and duties of faculty members across different fields of study.

Furthermore, it is important for institutions to acknowledge the influence of demographic factors, such as age and overall work experience, on the effectiveness of performance management systems (PMS). In order to optimise outcomes, institutions should customise their PMS strategies to cater to the unique demands and career stages of individuals. Less experienced faculty members and those who are younger can gain advantages from mentorship programmes, focused training opportunities, and early career support efforts that are integrated within PMS frameworks. These activities aim to promote their development and effectiveness in teaching, research, and service.

Furthermore, although gender did not have a significant impact on the association between PMS and faculty performance in this study, it is important for institutions to continue addressing gender equality concerns in academic environments. This encompasses guaranteeing equitable access to resources, chances for leadership and professional development, and proactive strategies to counteract biases in performance assessment and career progression procedures.

Moreover, it is crucial to consistently monitor and evaluate the success of PMS in order to identify specific areas that require improvement and adjustment as time progresses. Institutions should actively involve faculty members in continual communication and feedback loops to assess the influence of PMS on their professional growth and work contentment, promoting a culture of constant enhancement and attentiveness to faculty requirements". Finally, further investigation should focus on longitudinal studies and mixed-methods approaches to enhance our comprehension of how PMS impacts faculty performance over time and in various institutional settings. An examination of the interconnectedness of demographic determinants and an exploration of novel PMS (Performance Management System) strategies could yield useful insights for improving faculty involvement, retention, and overall effectiveness within higher education institutions". By adopting these suggestions, higher education institutions in Delhi/NCR can utilise performance management systems as

strategic instruments to empower teachers, foster academic excellence, and maintain institutional growth in a changing educational environment.

References

- 1) Aguinis, H. (2019). *Performance Management for Dummies*. John Wiley & Sons.
- 2) Boud, D., & Molloy, E. (2013). *Feedback in Higher and Professional Education: Understanding It and Doing It Well*. Routledge.
- 3) Brett, J. F., & Atwater, L. E. (2001). 360-degree feedback: Accuracy, reactions, and perceptions of usefulness. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(5), 930-942.
- 4) Brown, M., & Benson, J. (2003). Rated to exhaustion? Reactions to performance appraisal processes. *Industrial Relations Journal*, 34(1), 67-81.
- 5) Brown, T., & Green, H. (2022). Performance management systems in higher education: Trends and challenges. *Journal of Educational Management*, 35(2), 123-140.
- 6) Buchner, T. W. (2007). Performance management theory: A look from the performer's perspective with implications for HRD. *Human Resource Development International*, 10(1), 59-73.
- 7) Chaudhary, R., & Patel, S. (2023). Moderating effects of demographic variables on performance management in higher education. *International Journal of HRM*, 44(3), 567-589.
- 8) Cho, K., & MacArthur, C. (2010). Student revision with peer and expert reviewing. *Learning and Instruction*, 20(4), 328-338.
- 9) Colquitt, J. A., Conlon, D. E., Wesson, M. J., Porter, C. O. L. H., & Ng, K. Y. (2001). Justice at the millennium: A meta-analytic review of 25 years of organizational justice research. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 425-445.
- 10) Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behavior*. Springer.
- 11) DeNisi, A. S., & Pritchard, R. D. (2006). Performance appraisal, performance management and improving individual performance: A motivational framework. *Management and Organization Review*, 2(2), 253-277.
- 12) Erdogan, B. (2002). Antecedents and consequences of justice perceptions in performance appraisals. *Human Resource Management Review*, 12(4), 555-578.
- 13) Falchikov, N., & Goldfinch, J. (2000). Student peer assessment in higher education: A meta-analysis comparing peer and teacher marks. *Review of Educational Research*, 70(3), 287-322.
- 14) Gagné, M., & Deci, E. L. (2005). Self-determination theory and work motivation. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26(4), 331-362.
- 15) Garrett, L. E. (2011). The Use of Technology in Performance Management. *Performance Improvement*, 50(9), 26-31.
- 16) Greller, M. M., & Herold, D. M. (1975). Feedback: A necessary condition for the goal setting-performance relationship. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 60(2), 174-179.

- 17) Gupta, P., & Bhardwaj, M. (2024). Higher education in Delhi/NCR: A comprehensive analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 29(1), 45-61.
- 18) Guskey, T. R. (2002). Professional development and teacher change. *Teachers and Teaching*, 8(3), 381-391.
- 19) Ilgen, D. R., Fisher, C. D., & Taylor, M. S. (1979). Consequences of individual feedback on behavior in organizations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 64(4), 349-371.
- 20) Jawahar, I. M., & Carr, D. (2007). Conscientiousness and contextual performance: The compensatory effects of perceived organizational support and leader-member exchange. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(4), 330-349.
- 21) Johnson, L., Smith, R., & Thompson, A. (2020). Enhancing faculty performance through effective performance management systems. *Journal of Higher Education Policy*, 18(4), 289-305.
- 22) Kanfer, R., & Ackerman, P. L. (2004). Aging, adult development, and work motivation. *Academy of Management Review*, 29(3), 440-458.
- 23) Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (1996). *The Balanced Scorecard: Translating Strategy into Action*. Harvard Business Press.
- 24) Khan, M., & Ahmad, N. (2021). Performance management systems in higher education institutions: A systematic review. *Education and Society*, 22(3), 201-219.
- 25) Kluger, A. N., & DeNisi, A. (1996). The effects of feedback interventions on performance: A historical review, a meta-analysis, and a preliminary feedback intervention theory. *Psychological Bulletin*, 119(2), 254-284.
- 26) Knight, P. T., Tait, J., & Yorke, M. (2006). The professional learning of teachers in higher education. *Studies in Higher Education*, 31(3), 319-339.
- 27) Kuvaas, B. (2011). The interactive role of performance appraisal reactions and regular feedback. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 26(2), 123-137.
- 28) Latham, G. P., Borgogni, L., & Petitta, L. (2008). Goal setting and performance management in the public sector. *International Public Management Journal*, 11(4), 385-403.
- 29) Levy, P. E., & Williams, J. R. (2004). The social context of performance appraisal: A review and framework for the future. *Journal of Management*, 30(6), 881-905.
- 30) Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2002). Building a practically useful theory of goal setting and task motivation: A 35-year odyssey. *American Psychologist*, 57(9), 705-717.
- 31) London, M. (2003). *Job Feedback: Giving, Seeking, and Using Feedback for Performance Improvement*. Psychology Press.
- 32) Mishra, S., & Kaur, J. (2021). Age as a moderating factor in performance management systems in academia. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 40(2), 315-332.
- 33) Ng, T. W. H., & Feldman, D. C. (2010). The relationships of age with job attitudes: A meta-analysis. *Personnel Psychology*, 63(3), 677-718.

- 34) O'Laughlin, E. M., & Bischoff, L. G. (2005). Balancing parenthood and academia: Work/family stress as influenced by gender and tenure status. *Journal of Family Issues*, 26(1), 79-106.
- 35) Pulakos, E. D. (2009). *Performance Management: A New Approach for Driving Business Results*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- 36) Rao, V., Sharma, P., & Kumar, S. (2022). Gender dynamics in performance management: A study of higher education institutions. *Gender Studies in Education*, 15(1), 78-94.
- 37) Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 54-67.
- 38) Sharma, R., & Verma, A. (2021). Impact of performance management systems on faculty performance in Indian HEIs. *Management Education Journal*, 32(2), 104-118.
- 39) Singh, A., & Gupta, R. (2020). Quality education and performance management: The Indian scenario. *Journal of Higher Education Research*, 25(3), 199-214.
- 40) Sitzmann, T., Ely, K., Brown, K. G., & Bauer, K. N. (2010). Self-assessment of knowledge: A cognitive learning or affective measure? *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 9(2), 169-191.
- 41) Smither, J. W., London, M., & Reilly, R. R. (2005). Does performance improve following multisource feedback? A theoretical model, meta-analysis, and review of empirical findings. *Personnel Psychology*, 58(1), 33-66.
- 42) Spencer, L. M., & Spencer, S. M. (1993). *Competence at Work: Models for Superior Performance*. John Wiley & Sons.
- 43) Steelman, L. A., Levy, P. E., & Snell, A. F. (2004). The feedback environment scale: Construct definition, measurement, and validation. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 64(1), 165-184.
- 44) Thomas, S. R., Martin, R., & Apigian, C. H. (2015). Instructor and student use of peer review in the assessment of student work. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning*, 12(2), 61-70.
- 45) Van der Rijt, J., Van den Bossche, P., Van de Wiel, M. W., Segers, M. S., & Gijsselaers, W. H. (2012). The role of individual and organizational characteristics in feedback seeking behavior in the initial career stage. *Human Resource Development International*, 15(3), 283-300.